

Data Pitch

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D5.3 Round 1: Final Review

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1. Executive summary

Deliverable 5.3 has been produced to provide a summary of the first round of the acceleration phase of Data Pitch, the lessons learned by the partners, and the best practices that can be extracted from the programme and applied in the second round of acceleration and similar future programmes.

As a consortium, the Data Pitch partners have, so far and in this first round, successfully accelerated 18 startups over a 6 month period. This 6 month acceleration period will be approaching its end by the time this report will be delivered. The startups originate from 10 different European countries, and are developing either a product or service that builds upon shared data.

The report highlights a number of fundamental lessons learned by the Data Pitch partners which were gathered through direct feedback from startups; the main ones are the value of the bi-weekly 1-2-1 with the Data Pitch advisors, which keep startups engaged and the programme team able to track their performance on a regular basis. Remote peer-to-peer support, on the other hand, has proven to be more challenging but was achieved through the organised face-to-face events. The lessons learned are the following:

- Data Providers are a fundamental stakeholder of the programme and need to be actively involved and engaged.
- A voluntary mentorship programme tends to result in low engagement of mentors with the startups.
- More industry and technical expertise are needed, both for mentoring and review.
- Needed more networking opportunities, in particular with corporates and investors.
- Peer-to-peer support is challenging considering remote acceleration but can be leveraged from face-to-face events .
- Bi-weekly reports are an effective way of tracking activities and monitoring progress.
- A standalone pitch and networking event is challenging to organize and not effective in attracting a large enough audience of corporates and investors.
- There is value in involving all programme partners in the acceleration phase.
- Bi-weekly 1-2-1 advisorship meetings are a good way to keep the startups engaged and to track their performance.

The report includes recommendations for improvements to the second round of acceleration and future programmes, such as creating further networking opportunities between startups, corporates and investors; improving the engagement with mentors, and having a more rigorous formal process to track activities and successes through the acceleration.

2. Introduction

This deliverable summarises the activities, key metrics, lessons learned and best practices that have been achieved as part of WP5. The deliverable reviews the processes designed to track startups' progress and the services that have been offered to the startups throughout the length of the acceleration, before identifying the lessons learned by the partners, and concluding with recommendations for improvement on future programmes similar to Data Pitch.

The report documents the activities that have been undertaken by both the startups and the partners in line with the Data Pitch acceleration programme. These activities are identified under the tracking of progress and services provided, which included the mentorship programme, the perks and offers, advisorship, networking, events, PR & communication.

This document was produced before the end of the first round, therefore some of the results are not final, and some of the events are described as planned; these cases are clearly mentioned.

3. Context

Work package (WP) 5 focuses on the support provided to SMEs and startups through the accelerator programme. The main goal for this WP was to set up a partnership programme which, besides equity-free grant investment and marketing support, included mentoring and coaching sessions, as well as peer-to-peer support and networking.

Round 1 of the acceleration programme was run over the course of 6 months from February to July 2018. The support was provided throughout the duration of the acceleration. Some activities will continue to be provided for a period beyond the life of the project such as mentoring, and tools that offer startups the opportunity to network with each other such as Slack.

The programme engaged with multiple audiences to ensure the survival and growth of the startups throughout the acceleration. By providing the startups with grant funding the partners also had an obligation to ensure the agreed KPIs, deliverables and work plans are adhered to.

4. Overview of the acceleration activities

This section describes the activities that have been carried out by the Data Pitch consortium and especially those partners involved in WP5. This section will focus on the services that have been provided to the startups during their acceleration period and the processes put in place to track their progress during the programme. In addition this section will include information on feedback from the startups and key metrics that have been achieved by both the startups and the partners involved.

4.1. Key Onboarding Documents & Processes

To facilitate the startups onboarding, the partners designed a number of supporting documents and put in place processes ready for the start of the acceleration phase.

4.1.1 Startup Handbook

All startups received a [Startup Handbook](#) before the start of their acceleration. The handbook served as a introduction and overview of the acceleration programme, providing all the necessary details for startups to have a smooth onboarding to the programme. It was treated as a live document, being updated with relevant information as necessary.

The main content of this Startup Handbook was information regarding the programme schedule, points of contact, perks and online community tools (e.g. Slack, mailing lists etc), communication materials (Data Pitch logo, Twitter, Facebook page), and information regarding the mentorship, acceleration events and milestones.

4.1.2 Accelerator Schedule

Partners created a detailed schedule for the acceleration period so that all the startups were aware of all activities and events. The schedule included information on advisor meetings, team meetings, dates for bi-weekly reports, milestones and face-to-face events.

Besides providing an overview of all the activities to the startups, drawing up the schedules resulted in better up-front planning of the acceleration phase and enabled the partners to plan their own activities.

4.1.3 Youtube video of application process

The partners created a [Youtube video](#) to help support startups and SMEs who were looking to apply to the programme. This video contains a step-by-step process describing how to complete the open application.

4.2. Tracking of progress

4.2.1 Work plans

Tracking the progress and activities of the startups during the acceleration period followed a work plan structure. Each startup submitted their work plan for the acceleration period which detailed the activities, deliverables and KPIs they would undertake over the 6 months period. These were

assessed and reviewed by the partners during the negotiation period (from November 2017 to January 2018) and were used as basis for tracking and monitoring the development and performance of each startup during the acceleration period.

Once the acceleration started, the process of ensuring that funds were spent appropriately began. In order to do this, the partners had to track the progress made, and did so via a number of methods.

4.2.2 Bi-weekly reports

In order to manage the progress of the startups' activities against their negotiated work plans, a tracking system was put in place to receive updates from each company on a bi-weekly basis. Each startup will have completed 12 bi-weekly reports (2 per month) by the end of the acceleration. These reports also allowed the partners to monitor the impact of the programme in various metrics. Monitoring of these metrics produced many benefits: It enabled the advisors to identify areas where startups required more focus and effort; the advisors could identify areas where startups would benefit from more in-depth peer-to-peer support or mentorship; in addition, the advisors could identify success stories that could be used in promotion of the programme.

An online tool called Airtable was used to build and aggregate these reports. Airtable is described in more detail in deliverable D5.2 Experiments Oversight Tools.

A template of the bi-weekly report can be found on Annex 1.

4.2.3 Milestone reports

In conjunction with the bi-weekly reports startups had to submit 3 milestone reports during their acceleration. The grant funding was split across the 6 month period and payment was linked to these milestone reports. The idea was to manage expectations throughout the acceleration, and to highlight any changes to the activities as originally agreed.

By using milestone reports as a way of tracking, partners were able to identify differences between the work plan and the recent tasks undertaken. Additionally, this gave both the partners and the companies a chance to review the associated costs and to discuss any reporting issues.

Having this tracking method in place enabled a consistent approach when dealing with a number of startups at any given time. This approach also gave partners the time to mitigate against any problems or issues picked up in the reporting.

Having an added layer of sign-off linked to payment acted as an incentive for startups to adhere to deadlines and provide well detailed reports.

4.2.4 Milestone Reviews

For each of the two milestones with payments attached - milestones 2 and 3 - the partners have introduced an additional face-to-face review meeting.

These face-to-face reviews were attended by the startup's advisor and at least 2 reviewers, either from the programme partners or external. The reviewers were selected based on their expertise, with one more business focused and the other having a technical background. The purpose of the review was to objectively evaluate the startup's journey so far by analysing and comparing their activities, KPI's and deliverables against that of their original work plan. Depending on their

progress against the work plan the reviewers would recommend whether to pass, conditionally-pass or fail the startups to progress to the next stage. This resulted in a more unbiased evaluation of the startups.

Milestone 2 Review

This review was combined with the Demonstration Day and happened in Lisbon on May 17th and 18th. It was attended by the advisors and reviewers from the following consortium partners: Beta-i, ODI, and University of Southampton.

Each startup was given a 30 minutes slot, which consisted of a 10 minutes timed presentation followed by 15 minutes Q&A and 5 minutes of feedback from the startup on the programme.

Since this review happened before the end of the milestone, there was no binding pass or fail decision for the startups, but instead the reviewers provided guidance on what was needed to successfully pass once the formal Milestone Review Template was submitted.

Milestone 3 Review - Final Review

This review will take place after this document is submitted. It is planned to take place in London on June 26th and 27th. It will be attended by the advisors and reviewers from all the consortium partners, and potentially external reviewers assigned by the European Commission.

Each startup will be given an hour slot consisting of a 15 minute timed presentation followed by 15 minutes Q&A. The startups will then be invited to step out, while the panel spends a maximum of 20 minutes evaluating their progress through the programme. This is where the decision to either pass, conditionally pass or fail the startups will occur. Once a decision is made, the final 10 minutes will consist of communication of the final decision and evaluator feedback. Once the feedback is supplied, each startup will be given the opportunity to reflect on the programme itself and to provide feedback for improvement.

4.3. Services offered

4.3.1 Training

Workshops

Startups have been able to engage with a number of workshops throughout the acceleration. These workshops run every other two weeks, either remotely or face-to-face during programme events (e.g. Kick off, Demonstration Day). Whenever possible efforts were made to record these workshops for later viewing by the participating startups, as part of an open training catalogue, and as part of the dissemination and exploitation strategy.

The workshops delivered during the round 1 were:

- Introduction to the GDPR (face-to-face)
- How to craft contagious content (face-to-face)
- How to run successful marketing campaigns
- B2B Sales
- Fundraising 101
- How to raise a seed round
- Getting press

- An introduction to anonymisation assessment (face-to-face)
- How to do twice as much in half the time (face-to-face)
- Defining your purpose and values

Founder stories

For startups to learn from other entrepreneurs and similar experiences we run a “founder stories” event once every 2 months. These focus on the startup journeys of other startups, including past programmes. These are less formal and not recorded.

The founder stories delivered during Round 1 were:

- Iban Benzal from WildChef formerly RentSquare (face-to-face at Kick off)
- Damiano Ramazzotti from Wetipp
- Daniel Araújo from Attentive (face-to-face at the Demonstration Day)

4.3.2 Advisorship

For the duration of the acceleration period each startup was provided with a dedicated point of contact to act as their advisor. The partners who provided advisory during Round 1 were: the Open Data Institute (ODI) and Beta-i. Each advisor was allocated between 5 to 8 startups to work with. Each advisor provided peer-to-peer support, helped create introductions within their networks, provided coaching and mentoring, as well as suggesting events for the startups to attend. This relationship proved invaluable when ensuring the startups adhered to their work plans.

Advisorship took these three structured forms:

- Bi-weekly 1-2-1's between the advisor and each startup to ensure alignment and progression within the programme. Those consisted of 30 minute meetings via video conference, all pre-scheduled from the beginning of the acceleration and included in the Accelerator Schedule. The minutes of these meetings were reported in Airtable as a means to centralize the information regarding progress of the startups and make it available for all the partners of the program.
- Bi-weekly Team Meetings with all the startups and advisors, happening on the same weeks as the above mentioned bi-weekly 1-2-1's to ensure alignment with the programme and to communicate relevant information from the programme to the cohort, but also to promote sharing and networking between the startups. Those consisted of 30 minute meetings via video conference, all pre-scheduled from the beginning of the acceleration and included in the Accelerator Schedule.
- Advisor Group Meetings between the advisor and the group of startups under her/his advisorship, to serve as an additional means of assuring alignment and progression but also to promote sharing and networking between the startups in a more intimate environment. Those consisted of 1 hour meetings via video conference, held at the advisor's request with at least 2 weeks notice, and no more than 2 per month, typically on opposite weeks from the above mentioned Bi-weekly 1-2-1's.

4.3.3 Mentorship

The programme currently has 25 mentors that are available for startup mentoring and support. These mentors offer a breadth of experience and skills related to both business and technology fields. The partners constantly look to add further value to the mentorship programme where relevant. New mentors will be sought or added to the programme if there is a gap identified; gaps are usually identified within advisory meetings when engaging directly with startups, or through startup bi-weekly reporting. Startups will outline the support they need from the programme which

is noted and acted upon once reports have been submitted.

Communication between startups and mentors is managed with the online tool Mentornity. Mentornity enables startups to search through a list of experts in the field, view their biographies, expertise and list of skills and book meetings with them. Mentors are tagged according to their skill so startups can easily filter through the list and find a mentor who suits their needs. Mentornity also functions as a communication tool between the two parties, where meetings can be booked and progress can be monitored.¹

4.3.4 Networking

During the acceleration period, the partners created networking opportunities for the startups to mingle and meet with potential corporate clients, investors or industry experts.

Online tools proved particularly useful as a form of networking, both as instant messaging (Slack) and mailing lists (Google Groups). The consortium learned that by facilitating online open networking opportunities, the challenge of time difference and geographical disparity could be reduced.

Slack played a vital role in the communication between startups and advisors, as it built a sense of community and enabled the teams to discuss opportunities. The informal and fast-paced style of Slack eliminated the lag time often experienced with emailing, and advisors were able to deal with pressing issues swiftly. Bespoke forums were set up for the startups and their cohort, keeping users up to date with events, new articles, success stories and relevant information. For a more formal means of communication from leaders of the programme, the mailing list on Google Groups also proved a useful tool.

Regular team meetings and advisor group meetings also provided networking opportunities and peer-to-peer support between the startups and partners (see above in the Advisorship chapter). They served as opportunities for the startups to share their progress with the cohort as well as openly request support from their peers.

Another form of networking was through the mentorship programme. Through coordinated contact between industry representatives and startups, we created a platform for tailored support. This support consisted of online interaction via emails and calls, and in-person mentoring on a 1-2-1 basis (more information on the Mentorship chapter above).

Events which required physical presence were a vital part of the networking (see below chapter on Events for more information). During programme events, the partners created specific opportunities for peer-to-peer support between the cohort and programme partners, the industry experts, data providers and potential clients and investors. These networking opportunities were highly valued by the startups and should be repeated whenever possible.

Additionally, the partners took efforts to provide introductions to industry experts, potential clients or investors, according to requests by the startups or needs identified by the advisors during the 1-2-1 meetings.

4.3.5 Offers & Perks

Throughout the accelerator we have offered startups and SMEs perks and discounts that provide them with daily support. In D5.1 Incubation Services, we identified initial perks that would be of

¹ D5.2 Experiments oversight tools:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1cwmpEAFu6jLJn6iEUUU4ODaWcNPauOff>

interest provide, including; AWS credits, Google Cloud credits and other project management related tools. As the programme has evolved, perks have included:

- ODI SME Membership
- Google Cloud Startup Program
- Amazon Web Services (AWS) Activate
- SendGrid's Accelerate program
- Free Lisbon Investment Summit tickets

Partners have also offered startups the opportunity to share their office spaces on an adhoc basis, providing startups with much needed work space and face-to-face support. To the ODI's knowledge, four startups have taken up this offer.

Full details of the perks and offers provided by Data Pitch are listed in the [startup handbook](#). This handbook is a live document that is updated as new perks are introduced.

4.3.6 Events

As part of the acceleration programme, the partners ran a series of face-to-face events, as well as promoting industry and startup related events.

Kick Off Meeting

To launch the start of the accelerator, Data Pitch organised a kick off event in London on the 1st and 2nd of February. The first day opened with an evening of pitches, introductions from the data providers, and networking with the press and members of the community. A filmographer was subcontracted to create a promotional [launch video](#) for use on the second call.

The second day launched the programme officially, with workshops for startups and meetings with advisors. This was the first opportunity for all startups to meet one another and their advisors and understand the requirements of the programme.

The purpose of the event was to create engagement within the cohort, for the whole team involved in the acceleration to meet in person and to start this phase with personal connections having already been made. The day ran smoothly and was well received by the startups.

The detailed agenda of the Kick Off is available on Annex 2.

Demonstration Day

The demonstration day was hosted at Beta-i in Lisbon on May 17th and 18th and was combined with the Milestone 2 review of startups. This was an opportunity to evaluate startups' progress in the accelerator, and to ensure that they were on track to achieve their goals. The demonstration day was a combination of workshops, talks, a pitch session and a networking session with the local ecosystem. A [video of the demonstration day](#) was created to use for promotion of the second call.

The detailed agenda of the Kick Off is available on Annex 3.

Demo Day

The demo day (planned for a date after the delivery of this report) will be an opportunity for the startups to showcase their products or solutions to an audience of corporates and investors in order to attract potential clients and funding.

To increase audience numbers, the demo day will be combined with another event aligned with Data Pitch in terms of objectives and audience type. At the time of writing, the demo day for round one is planned to happen during the ODI Summit, taking place in November in London.

Industry Events

Partners have looked to support startups by identifying relevant and events around Europe, in particular events with a high investor attendance. Communication around this involves notifications about events, potential speaking opportunities and discounts on tickets. We have acquired discounts on the following events:

- Rise of the AI - Munich
- Unbound - London
- Lisbon Investment Summit - Lisbon
- Sprinters - London

4.3.7 HR Recruitment Support

To support the startups with finding and recruiting talent, the programme has created a specific job posting area on the Data Pitch website. These jobs can then easily be shared online. This helps the startups to publish jobs for free and also raises awareness for the programme.

A form was created to collect specific job details such as title, location, skills required and other relevant information to engage the right candidates.

4.3.8 PR & Communication

Partners promoted successes of the startups within the programme by sharing news on different social media and communications channels. This brings external exposure to our startups, and creates further opportunities for them to exploit. A full list of activities can be found in [D6.5 Summary of activities and Impact V1](#).

4.4. Key metrics

This section details the key metrics achieved in the first acceleration period. These metrics will contribute to the evaluation of the programme's success, against the KPI's that were initially defined. Some of these KPI's consisted of:

- 400% return on investment (ROI)
- 50 - 100 companies incubated
- 50 investors
- 5 - 10 investments

The partners of Data Pitch were tasked with granting an investment fund of €4.9M. The aim of this fund was to provide startups and SMEs with grant funding up to €100k per startup. In order to manage this fund amongst the high volume of startups, the partners distributed it over two cohorts

of companies.

The first cohort featured 18 funded companies which were accelerated for six months, from February to July 2018. The largest percentage of startups and SMEs that received funding originated from the United Kingdom (3) and Germany (3). The geographic reach of Data Pitch-funded organisations ranged from Germany to Estonia, totalling 11 different countries in varying industries across Europe (see Figure).

Figure 1: Startup and SME country of origin and industry

Throughout the acceleration, the partners have been monitoring the startups and SMEs by measuring their overall impact, including the amount of jobs created, sales figures and further investment received (see figure below).

Figure 2: Metrics of startups/SME's

4.5. Feedback

In order to provide the best services possible to the startups in both rounds, the partners made efforts to capture structured feedback from the startups throughout the acceleration programme.

Some of the formats for capturing feedback from the startups were as follows:

- Kick off feedback form
- Bi-weekly reports. On each bi-weekly report there is a specific section for feedback with the following question: “Do you have any feedback on the programme so far, i.e. team briefings?”. At the time of writing, 12 startups have given their feedback through this medium.
- Advisor 1-2-1 meetings. During the bi-weekly 1-2-1 meetings, the advisors gather informal feedback from the startups. This feedback is part of the meeting minutes and can be accessed on Airtable.
- Milestone review templates. On each of the milestone review templates (one for each of the three milestones) the final section includes the feedback questions: “What can the consortium partners do to help you further?” and “Is there anything else you'd like to tell us?”
- Milestone 2 review. During the milestone 2 review, each startup was requested to provide feedback on the programme, in particular on the services offered.
- Demonstration day feedback form. After the demonstration day, the partners sent startups a formal feedback form to understand how valuable the day was to attendees.

Annex 4 provides an extract of the most relevant feedback provided by the startups – the most positive points and the most critical points for improvement. This information will be fed in to the planning of round two to make improvements.

5. Lessons learned

Recognising insights and reflections made during the acceleration programme is crucial to learning how to improve the programme. The lessons learned will form the basis of recommendations for any future programmes. So far, the key lessons include:

Data providers are a fundamental stakeholder of the programme and need to be actively involved and engaged.

During the acceleration phase, it was noted that the partners put most of the effort into the relationship and engagement of the startups, as it was assumed that the data providers were already involved enough with the programme not to require further action or assistance from the partners.

It became clear that without an active effort from the programme to continue engagement with the data providers, it would delay results and create entropy in the relationship between the data providers and startups.

A voluntary mentorship programme tends to result in low engagement of mentors with the

startups.

The mentorship programme in Data Pitch is based on the voluntary participation of the mentors. Engagement with Mentornity is also voluntary.

Whereas startups actively reached out to mentors, the mentors did not actively contact the startups to offer their support.

More industry and technical expertise are needed, both for mentoring and review.

The programme had several mentors with business and technical knowledge. However, there were very few mentors with specific sector expertise (e.g. health & wellness, tourism) and few reviewers with technical expertise.

The partners realised that industry expertise would be the most valuable for the startups, not only because they could further relate to and assist the startups with this knowledge, but also to provide other valuable industry contacts. This type of expertise is useful in informing the partners of specific industry requirements and trends that might be fundamental to help guide startups.

Additionally, technical expertise is fundamental when reviewing the startups progress, mostly on milestone reviews.

More networking opportunities are needed, in particular with corporates and investors.

Forming the right connections and partnerships is crucial in business, especially in the early stages of a company's life. The startups learned the importance of being a recognised part of the startup ecosystem and they made use of networking opportunities to attain the contacts needed to penetrate their intended markets. Events also provided key opportunities to showcase and promote their product or service. With limited funds, and the need to scale quickly, partners learned that networking opportunities are the startups' best way to grow and advertise.

Peer-to-peer support can be challenging when done remotely, and is best done at face-to-face events.

Peer-to-peer support should be one of the major sources of support in a startup acceleration programme. However it is very challenging to do well remotely, given that companies operate in different sectors, markets and countries.

Nevertheless, the partners made special efforts to foster these interactions. Slack was used to improve communication and support groups were introduced during face-to-face events such as the demonstration day, where participants could discuss their common struggles.

Verbal feedback from the startups after events evidenced that communication was continued online and some level of peer-to-peer support was maintained.

Bi-weekly reports are an effective way of tracking activities and monitoring progress.

By requesting a bi-weekly report from each startup, each advisor could track their activities and evaluate ongoing impact. Making this a regular process meant that advisors found it easy to monitor and compare the activities against the original work plan. This allowed any issues to be raised quickly and provided the foundations for the advisorship.

This process did not just prove valuable to the partners, it also received a positive response from

the startups themselves. It was felt that by tracking progress continuously, startups were able to visualise their success, growth and progression throughout the acceleration. It also played a vital role when completing the milestone reports, as all costs and efforts had been accounted for.

The partners also learned the value of monitoring progress in this way. Whereas the startups were tasked with following the work plan they had initially set, the startup ecosystem requires companies to be adaptable. By tracking progress, partners were able to see which KPI's were not being met and could provide the support needed to keep them on track.

A standalone pitching or networking event does not match result to effort.

It is highly recommended that the startups participate in an event where they can showcase their products / solutions to a wide audience of potential customer and investors.

During round one, the partners organised the demonstration day which required a lot of logistical planning. However, there was not enough participation from corporate figures or investors, either in person or remotely through the livestream.

It was noted that the desired audience is difficult to attract between the many other similar events available and other work commitments.

There is value in involving all programme partners in the acceleration phase.

During round one, most of the WP5 and acceleration activities were performed by ODI and Beta-i, as the other programme partners were focused on different work package and phases of the programme.

However, the partners realised that it was useful, both for the programme and the startups, to have some level of involvement from all the other partners as well. This is because it would improve partner knowledge of the startups, their relationship with data providers and other actors in the data ecosystem, as well as enabling informal mentoring to occur.

Bi-weekly 1-2-1 advisorship meetings are a good method for keeping the startups engaged and tracking their performance.

Although 1-2-1 advisorship meetings require a high level of effort from the programme partners, it was considered to be the best way to maintain the high level of engagement from the startups and to keep an open channel of communication between parties.

6. Recommendations

In order to provide suitable recommendations for programme improvement, we must reflect on some of the lessons learned. The lessons will provide us with the foundation which we can build upon and improve the services provided. Below outlines our method for mitigating identified challenges in future programmes.

Lesson: Data providers are fundamental stakeholders of the programme and need to be actively involved and engaged.

Recommendation: In the same way that the programme maintained an open communication with the startups to keep them engaged and track their performance, a similar effort should be put in place to engage the data providers.

Lesson: A voluntary mentorship programme tends to result in low engagement of mentors with the startups.

Recommendation: In order to encourage higher mentor engagement in the programme, mentors should be used as facilitators for the workshops and be invited to face-to-face events.

Lesson: More industry and technical expertise are needed, both for mentoring and review.

Recommendation: The programme partners should make an effort to procure and involve industry and technical experts, either from their own organisation or from their network. Once the cohort has been selected, it will become clear which industries and technologies will be needed.

Lesson: More networking opportunities are needed, in particular with corporates and investors.

Recommendation: It has been identified that networking is the most important service that the programme can provide. Therefore, additional efforts should be made to organise events, send startups to industry events and provide contacts according to the startups needs.

Lesson: Peer-to-peer support is challenging to do remotely.

Recommendation: If possible, at the beginning of the acceleration phase, the programme should organise a face-to-face kick off event which connects startups with their advisors, as well as other startups. Getting the team to form bonds at an early stage will improve the quality of remote support.

Lesson: Bi-weekly reports are an effective way of tracking activities and monitoring progress.

Recommendation: Tracking startups' activities via bi-weekly reports added to the success of the programme, and should therefore be implemented again. A further process could be implemented whereby startups are obliged to carry out the recommendations given to them from report reviewers.

Lesson: A standalone pitch and networking event does not attract enough corporates and investors.

Recommendation: Instead of organising a singular event, which requires a lot of administration and logistical planning, programme events should be integrated into existing events with a large

audience and similar target. They should take place during or after the last months of the acceleration phase.

Lesson: There is value in involving all programme partners in the acceleration phase.

Recommendation: The acceleration work package leader and the partners most involved with this phase should include all other consortium partners in the acceleration where appropriate. Those partners should also be proactive in involving themselves in the acceleration.

Lesson: Bi-weekly 1-2-1 advisorship meetings are a good way to keep the startups engaged and to track their performance.

Recommendation: The 1-2-1 bi-weekly advisorship meetings are a fundamental part of the performance tracking and startup engagement and should be pursued in the second round of acceleration or any future similar programmes. If possible, some of those meetings should be face-to-face, but remote video calls have also proved to be effective.

These recommendations should be considered when undertaking round two of Data Pitch, as well as similar acceleration programmes. By incorporating these recommendations, future programmes will be able to achieve a similar success.

7. Conclusion

This evaluation has detailed the best practices and changes that should be implemented in the second round of acceleration and in future programmes similar to Data Pitch.

The partners identified a number of recommendations including: monitoring and evaluating of the startups using the various metrics; providing networking opportunities; involving both Data Providers and all programme partners in the acceleration phase; and, actively engaging with startups through various communication channels to keep track of companies' performance throughout the programme.

As this report was produced before the start of round two, Data Pitch will have the opportunity to implement some of the recommendations presented above. This will contribute to an increase in the quality of the programme and a more efficient use of resources.

8. Annexes

Annex 1: Bi-weekly report template

Data Pitch biweekly progress reports

Let us know what you are up to, what you have achieved and how we can help.

What is your company name?

+ Add

Which report is this?

Add an option

What did you achieve in the last two weeks?

What would you like to tell the world?

What are you going to do in the next two weeks?

What is the total amount of sales in the last two weeks in Euros? (example format: 5,000)

What is the total amount of investments (Grants, BAs, VCs...) in the last two weeks in Euros? (example format: 5,000)

What is the total amount of realised efficiencies in the last two weeks in Euros? (example format: 5,000)

Have you increased or decreased number of employed by your company including the founders (only project employees)?

Are you looking for additional funding/investments etc... at this time?

Do you have any feedback on the programme so far? i.e. Team briefings

Any other comments?

Field 1

Field 2

What is your company name?

Submit

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Annex 2: Agenda of kick off

Kick off Reception - Thursday 1st of February 2017

Runway East

<https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/data-pitch-kick-off-tickets-41401997489>

18:00 **Reception starts**

18:15 Introduction to the event - Jeni Tennison - Open Data Institute CEO

18:30 Welcome word from Data Pitch PO - Francesco Barbato - EU Commission

18:45 Introduction to Data Pitch from Project Coordinator - Elena Simperl - University of Southampton

19:00 Intro to Data Pitch partners - Data Provider

19:15 Startup elevator pitches (1 min pitch) - 30 min

20:00 Drinks and Networking

22:00 End

Kick off Day 2 - Friday 2nd of February

9:00 - 10:00 Welcome from Data Pitch. Introduction of our team.

10:00 - 10:45 The accelerator schedule and expectations.

10:45 - 11:00 Coffee break 15min

11:00 - 12:15 Group meetings with advisors 1h ([ODI HQ](#) & [Runway East](#))

12:15 - 13:30 Lunch 1h lunch - 15 min allowance to change location ([ODI HQ](#) & [Runway East](#))

13:30 - 14.30 Session on data protection and GDPR - Sophie University of Southampton

14:30 - 14.45 Coffee break

14:45 - 15:30 Workshop on "how to get "word of mouth" for your startup" - Bashara - Beta-i

15:30 - 16:00 Founder story - Iban Benzal from Wild Chef formerly RentSquare

16:00 - 16:15 Closing Greetings

16:30 - End

Annex 3: Agenda of Demonstration Day

Thursday, May 17th	
14h30	Welcome and agenda (15m)
14h45	<p>Workshop: An introduction to anonymisation assessment</p> <p>We are developing an interactive e-learning tool to assess anonymisation practices. As part of the workshop, we would like start-ups to test the tool and answer a short questionnaire on its usefulness and user-friendliness. We will use this feedback to make any necessary amendments to the tool before its release in June 2018 (as part of D3.5). There will be opportunity for an answer/question session on anonymity and data protection law (an open forum) at the end of the workshop.</p> <p>Any requirements for the start-ups:</p> <p>(1) BYOD – Please could start-ups bring their own devices in order to utilise the interactive tool</p> <p>(2) Questionnaire – After start-ups have utilised the tool, they will be asked to fill in a brief questionnaire (to be completed before the end of the workshop) about its utility and usability.</p> <p>Any special room/logistics requirements: WiFi access and a screen to display PowerPoint slides.</p>
16h15	Coffee Break
16h30	Milestone 2 Review
Friday, May 18th	
9h30	Discuss / Align reviews (30m)
10h00	Milestone 2 Review
11h30	Coffee Break + Discuss / Align reviews
12h00	Milestone 2 Review
13h	Lunch
14h30	Workshop: Agile Workshop - How to do twice as much in half the time
16h00	Founder Story / CEO Talk
17h	Open Pitch Session (part of Lisbon Entrepreneurship Week) with live webcast
18h15	1-on-1 tables
18h00 21h30	TGiLEW - Thank God it's Lisbon Entrepreneurship Week (Networking Event)

Annex 4: Extract of relevant startup feedback

Positive feedback

- “Good support and processes”
- “Our advisor has been really helpful in keeping the focus and providing feedback on the work we do.”
- “We are so far very delighted with the support the programme has provided to us.”
- “Enjoyed very much the workshop about Data Protection”
- “Funding 101 story was useful”
- “The last session (regarding communication with investors) were quite helpful.”
- “Bi-weekly meetings are very useful”
- “Workshops work very well - Fund raising very relevant.”
- “Demonstration day is a good opportunity to share info and networking with other cohort's participants.”
- “The "middle review" (the demonstration) helps to soothe the anxiety of the final review”
- “Through Demonstration Day we got a good chance to feel the pulse on how things are going for us, receive valuable advice in workshop sessions, and networking and share experiences with other startups.”
- Demonstration Day was good for “Seeing other programme participants”
- Demonstration Day was good for “Talking in person to advisors”

Improvements needed

- “Identify a moment of how startups can be helping each other - foster more collaboration”
- “Get startups to run sessions”
- “Create exposure to potential customers, venture clients”
- “It would be great if startups could ask for help from other startups”
- “Thought there would be more engagement from Startups”
- “For the next call - involve more the whole teams of the startups - more knowledge sharing between the startups in a more structured way and not expect it to happen organically”
- “Would have appreciated matchmaking services as other acceleration programs do.”
- “I guess is difficult but more involvement from players outside Data Pitch (VCs, corporates)”